

Migrating Research Data to Another Repository

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Summary. Five years ago, we crafted a detailed scenario for migrating our research data from our locally-maintained, institutional repository to an external repository for which we had little control over. Now, with the rising cost of updating and maintaining our repository software to the latest version, we decided to realize the scenario step by step. We describe the challenges we encountered in the migration process.

1 Motivation

The maintenance of an institutional research data repository comes with substantial costs. While a large part of the efforts is devoted to data curation and ingestion as well as the communication with data depositors and consumers, there is a significant workload involved in keeping the repository software up-to-date. Costs related to software maintenance are rising, so we decided to migrate our research data to an external, infrastructural organization that is experienced with research data management, already hosts research data from a variety of other disciplines, and has trained staff. Five years ago, we crafted a workflow for this purpose (Trippel and Zinn, 2019). We have now put the workflow into motion and describe the challenges we encountered.

2 Technical background

Since 2010, our department offers a repository system to researchers of a Collaborative Research Centre in Linguistics. It holds around 650 data streams (mostly text-based, from psycholinguistic, experimental data to word embeddings), totaling around 600 gigabytes of storage. We started with a system based upon Fedora-Commons 3, which we extended with a number of bells and whistles (*e.g.*, a GUI to support data ingestion and rights management; an OAI-PMH port for data harvesting; export of ISO 24622-X (CMDI) based metadata with converters to Dublin Core and MARC-21). Due to security reasons, we later updated the

system to Fedora-Commons 4. Security patches available for this version where applied whenever possible.

3 Migration Process

All research data is being migrated to the university-wide repository (<https://fdat.uni-tuebingen.de/>), which organizes all data into research communities. A community to host data from the "Tübingen Archive for Language Resources" (TALAR) has been created in FDAT. The data archivists of the old (source) repository become the data curators of the new community in the (target) repository and keep their role as *data steward* for this community. Upon completion of the migration process, the old system is being shut down.

User authentication and authorization (AAI). A significant amount of research data was not publicly accessible in the source repository. The target repository has only limited AAI capabilities to restrict access. Data still under publication embargo will continue to be inaccessible to all users in the target repository. Interested parties must contact the data steward of the FDAT TALAR community. For new research data, our institution will continue to provide help to researchers who would like to archive their research data in a trusted, sustainable environment.

Metadata harmonization. In the source repository, all research data was described using CMDI-based metadata while the target repository requires DataCite. During conversion, to minimize information loss, resource-specific metadata was written into DataCite's description fields. Moreover, the CMDI metadata becomes part of the data stream so that users can access the original metadata. Also, we will continue to operate an OAI-PMH provider that offers CMDI-based metadata to third parties, e.g., the Virtual Language Observatory (<https://vlo.clarin.eu>).

Persistent identification. Each dataset in the source repository was accessible through a persistent identifier using the handle system. Part identifiers were used to address individual files of a dataset. The target repository makes use of the DOI system. We therefore mapped the legacy handle to the DOI while omitting all part identifiers.

Bibliography

Thorsten Trippel and Claus Zinn, "Lessons Learned: On the Challenges of Migrating a Research Data Repository from a Research Institution to a University Library". *Language Resources and Evaluation* 55, 191-207 (2021), Springer.